

SPECIFIC METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS' KNOWLEDGE OF SPORT TOURISM

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of the knowledge of the future physical education teachers about tourism are studied. Also, the principles of improving the system of training future physical education teachers and preparing them for pedagogical activities were analyzed.

Key words: physical education, sport, tourism, sports tourism, professional activity, training, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology.

INTRODUCTION. Pedagogical activities related to the improvement of the system of training pedagogues, bringing innovative approaches to it and thereby creating productive principles and models of training specialists are considered a priority task in the new stage of development of the society. This process is recognized by certain ideas in pedagogical education, which are related to the general laws of the development of modern society. In addition to attracting the attention of all specialists in the world, physical education as an education, its description (expression of content and essence) and classification (means, application processes) are expressed by scientists in different ways. Based on this, it can be said that physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at improving the human body morphologically and functionally, forming and improving basic movement skills, skills, and related knowledge that are important for his life.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Many studies have been conducted on the development of the professional skills of physical education and sports specialists, and the effective organization of the formation of moral values in athletes. aspects of mental, functional preparation; N.N. Tokhtaboyev, A.N. Shopulatov, S.S. Tajibayev, F. Kerimov, R. Abdumalikov, A. Muzaffarov, A. Mirzayev, A. Khudoyorov conducted research on improving the training of sports specialists using action games.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The principles of improving the training system of future physical education teachers and preparing them for pedagogical activity are built on the basis of the principles of convergence and divergence. physical activity, empathetic) are the priority areas of development of professional physical education, their development will help to form a professional, competitive and holistic personality of the graduate.

P.S. Gurevich defines the concept of a whole person as an idea of the same essence of a person, which is expressed through separate parts of the whole and at the same time through the whole. According to modern ideas, a whole is simultaneously a part of multiple wholes.

Another scientist, A. M. Navikov, identified the main directions of reforming pedagogical education as a whole system, in which he defined four main directions of educational goals: individual, society, production and education. the field itself. It includes

humanization, democratization of the education system, its progressive character, and orientation to continuous education as a lifelong learning.

Today, the issues of studying the will qualities of a person and forming new ways of doing it are gaining relevance. The current socio-political life on a global scale is the stage of the development of the individual society, which has such a characteristic that it is not the military power, but the psychological characteristics of the individual, willpower, intellectual potential, intelligence, thinking, new techniques and technologies that are of decisive importance. is enough.

Extreme tourism is travel and active types of recreation that are associated with risk in one way or another. Modern extreme tourism developed at the beginning of the 20th century, such as parachuting, mountaineering, rafting, etc. Extreme tourism requires not only physical fitness and courage. It is a type of tourism that is developed and widely spread in many European countries. Mostly young people are interested in this type of tourism and want to get real adrenaline. For this reason, Extreme tourism attracts more young people. Almost every type of extreme tourism requires training and skills. Currently, there are tens or even hundreds of types of extreme tourism, the most common of which are mountaineering, kayaking, diving, rafting, paragliding and mountain tourism. There is also an exotic type of extreme tourism.

Extreme tourism is not only one of the promising types of tourism business, it attracts more people. New unexplored places for extreme tourism are emerging, the emergence of new types of tourism is a proof of this. Extreme tourism is not only of high quality, but all its types require certain skills, appropriate equipment, experience and high professionalism.

Skydiving and paragliding are the most popular forms of extreme tourism recreation. Traditional parachute is especially popular in Ukraine due to its relatively cheap price.

Paragliders have personal equipment that allows them to make difficult jumps. These include group acrobatics, skysurfing, pole vaulting and others.

Rafting - swimming in mountain rivers using special devices.

Trekking is one of the most popular forms of sports tourism.

Mountaineering is one of the most extreme sports. Mountaineering requires excellent physical and psychological preparation, as well as special skills.

In recent years, significant reforms in the development of sports, extreme and recreational tourism have been implemented in our country. However, there are a number of other areas that require modern requirements and support. These include paragliding, hang gliding, aeronautics, small aviation, mountain tourism, bicycle tourism, skydiving, motor tourism, auto tourism.

Pedagogical experiences show that, based on the development of willpower in future physical education teachers, directing them to extreme sports and increasing their interest in sports tourism is one of the important socio-pedagogical tasks. Because interest is not enough to engage in sports tourism, forming a strong will is also important. Volitional qualities are formed in the process of the formation and acquisition of life experience of the personality and are an important practical task for every student, parent and pedagogue. As a person who has his own personal thoughts and principles in the current and future life of the growing young generation, he must be able to avoid various harmful habits and vices (smoking, alcoholism, drug addiction, etc.), study and Since the ability to overcome existing difficulties in the educational process in complex situations depends on the degree to which the system of

voluntary qualities of each person is developed, solving this task will affect the effectiveness of the student's current and future educational process, which is constantly becoming more and more complex and In addition to the growing training, it is also directly related to the activity of the club.

In our opinion, volitional behavior is goal orientation, self-control, refraining from one or another action when a situation arises, that is, mastering one's own behavior. The ability to control one's behavior is an important characteristic of an adult. "We can talk about the formation of personality only after acquiring personal behavior," writes L.S. Vygotsky. Volitional qualities are a feature of volitional organization, which is the manifestation of character in a specific situation, which requires overcoming difficulties.

A.T. According to Puni, "... the volitional qualities of each person appear as a whole system, but the structure of volitional qualities changes in different individuals, even as a result of the same person engaging in different activities. That is why volitional qualities are expressed as an interconnected, affected, moving, dynamic system. Volitional qualities are a specific aspect of volitional control that is manifested in specific situations related to character, formed when overcoming difficulties, and become personal characteristics.

The great psychologist V. I. Selivanov, who has been dealing with the issue of will for half a century, draws some conclusions based on the results of his personal experiences based on the basis of the study of will: 1) will is a person's own activity and self-control in the external world. description of forms of understanding; 2) will is considered a part of the whole consciousness of a person, and it applies to all forms and stages of consciousness; 3) will is a practical consciousness, a changing and reconstructing world, a state of conscious self-control by a person; 4) will is a characteristic of a person related to his emotions and intelligence, but it is not considered the motive of any action. Another scientist V.A. Krutetsky in his research includes consistency, independence, determination, discipline, courage, courage and diligence as part of will qualities. It touches on their definition, possibility of use, guidelines for formation. P. M. Yakobson divides the important qualities of will into independence, determination, perseverance, and self-mastery.

Researcher Y. P. Ilin has his own personal attitude to the qualities of will, which differs from the definition of other psychologists. In the colorful table compiled by the author, the quality of perseverance of the will is placed after perseverance in the order, and it is defined as follows: "Perseverance is the emergence of a continuous desire to achieve a goal, despite difficulties and failures." embodied in it in affirmative state. According to researcher D.N. Ushakov, the concept of "endurance" can mean the following meanings: 1) to endure unpleasant emotional situations without complaint, without regret, without taking any counter action; 2) to agree to the joke of fate without taking any counter-action, but waiting for changes; 3) suffering from a psychological condition; 4) to come to terms with something, not to worry about any excess experience, to bear the burden graciously; 5) to get used to following all things as much as possible; 6) not to rush; 7) create an opportunity to wait. As it can be seen from the comments, the originality and originality of the researcher D.N. Ushakov's comments are evident, but it is not the point to give him an expert assessment.

D. Priestley proposes to call the desire or desire formed after a person makes a decision to act as will. Because although the desired object is in front of our eyes, the desire to act does not always arise, for this there must be a desire to act. The scientist comes to the conclusion that these aspirations and actions are always determined by motives, and as a

result, there is always a reason for the will. V. Windelbandt understood the reality embodying individual desires and inclinations under the concept of will. The will is a complex of constant motives (desires) that characterizes the person and forms its basis.

It is known that volitional qualities are a mechanism of psychophysical regulation of human actions in physical education, and it is one of the personality traits that are manifested in the process of overcoming difficult situations. The manifestation of voluntary qualities in physical education is explained not only by striving for success and avoiding failure, but also by the formation of moral relations formed in a person. Currently, the voluntary training of future physical education teachers does not become urgent, but requires its further development.

As M.Y. Basov noted, the psychological methods of voluntary training in sports are sufficiently developed. In addition, the analysis of special literature showed that in the scientific-methodical works of a psychological and pedagogical nature, the interest in the problems of the athletes' will and volitional preparation has significantly decreased. So, will is an important feature of human activity, behavior and behavior, an important factor determining the content of his life. Consistency of activity and behavior is observed in a strong-willed person. The feeling of confidence in achieving the goal set before the person is the strength of the will and the main criterion. After all, firm belief creates the basis for overcoming difficulties on the way to achieving the goal, both physically and mentally. Each person has all the opportunities to develop the will and educate it independently. The sooner the process of consciously educating the will begins, the more success can be achieved.

CONCLUSION. From the theoretical analysis of the literature, it can be seen that self-regulation of future physical education teachers, as well as issues of developing primary willpower in them, are very important at the initial stage of sports training. Because this is considered a transition period, it is necessary to take into account a person's interests, ability to the field, level of motivation. "Persistence" is recognized as one of the qualities that are just being formed among the qualities of will in adolescence. Moreover, such conclusions are recognized by many advanced psychologists. Therefore, the formation of determination in young people engaged in physical education is one of the most important tasks.

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